

IMPORTANCE OF IMMUNE SYSTEM IN ISCHAEMIC HEART DISEASE IN WOMEN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8013645>

The adaptive immune response has recently emerged as an important factor in a wide range of cardiovascular diseases, including atherosclerosis, hypertension, cardiac remodelling and heart failure; however, its role is not fully understood. Since the recruitment of innate sensitive cells such as neutrophils and monocytes/macrophages coordinate with adaptive immunity such as T cells, dendritic cells and B cells, the temporal response and descriptions relating to the cellular phenotype and inflammatory processes in general need further research, clarification and consensus, especially in relation to cardiovascular disease. One of the widely studied and recently recognised topics in the physiology of the immune system is sex differences. Women are protected against cardiovascular disease before menopause, but the mechanisms of this surveillance are still unclear. Changes in hormonal status during menopause may stimulate pro-inflammatory and T cell-dependent responses and remove protection against hypertension. During pregnancy, women are closely monitored for hypertension because of the risk of pre-eclampsia for both mother and child. The influence of adaptive and innate immune cells on hypertension caused by placental ischaemia is well known; however the contribution of B1 lymphocytes versus B2 is unclear. All studies emphasise the complexity of the adaptive immune system in the development of cardiovascular disease. Unfortunately, there is no consensus on the optimal strategy for isolating and characterising immune cells from tissue.

Conclusion. The focus of the research community should be to develop a comprehensive range of mechanisms controlled by adaptive immunity in cardiovascular disease as a means of using these cells as therapeutic targets in cardiovascular medicine.